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Quality Assurance Techniques of Higher Education in Bangladesh: A Study

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Abstract

Throughout the world, higher education changes the society and is the center of change and development. Education without vision is fruitless and education without value is meaningless. Quality is not a destination rather it is a continuous journey. Quality means doing the right things right. Quality of higher education develops leadership qualities in people of different professions. Higher education can play an important role in facilitating these changes and producing adequately trained manpower in various fields. Quality assurance has become a major issue in higher education of Bangladesh due to all solution depends on quality assurance and higher education. This present study discussed the concepts of quality, quality of education; quality assurance highlighted and identified its challenges and techniques of quality education. It has highlighted the quality assurance principles for achieving quality education of its objectives. This paper also mentioned the main problems and development tools of quality assurance in higher education. It has concluded that quality assurance of higher education can play very significant role to promote social economic, technological, human resource development etc., which are highly correlated

Keywords: challenges; higher education; quality assurance; technique; teaching methods

1. Introduction

Education without vision is fruitless and education without value is meaningless. Quality is not a destination rather it is a continuous journey. Quality means doing the right things right. Doing things right is efficiency and doing right things is effectiveness. Quality education is the solution to all the problems and teachers are the main ingredients in giving quality education [1]. Quality comes out of a well structured process or system. This system refers institutional arrangements including infrastructure, evidence of good practices, and guiding principles for education. The quality assurance process includes designing academic programs with specific ILOs, strategies, implementation, and systematic review of the process to measure the effectiveness and continuous improvement.

Today, improving the quality is the biggest challenges before the higher education. Access to the global economy will depend more on the quality and productivity. This problem can be solved by making available more and more professional skills. It is the responsibility of the higher education system to ensure that skills, understanding and output of the students are equal to the best in the world. In this connection, teachers can play critical role in taking quality education and in shaping the future and destiny of a nation. Teachers teach the ways of life, channelize youth power and mold their character [2].

2. Review of Literature

Review of literature and important unrefined materials plays a vital role for building up a total infrastructure of a specific subject area in any type of research study. It helps the researcher to have an insight into the tested methods, procedures and interpretations of similar studies conducted elsewhere.

Kruase et al. [3], view a classroom as where teachers create enabling environment for students to know how to use the available time and resources, and also cooperate with their class mates to achieve quality learning. They also mentioned that the role of the teacher is to maximize learning and minimize disruptions by fostering among students' attitude of trust, tolerance, acceptance and cooperation.

Onyediniachi [4] indicates quality in education emphasizes teacher's competence, creativity and commitment, and how educational administrators organize institutional activities in order to realize the full potentials of all personnel in education institutions. It is the appropriateness and relevance of resources available for the achievement of educational goals and priorities, hence quality in education whether primary school, secondary school, or tertiary institutions require adequate inputs and output.

Borham and Ziarati [5] describes the quality assurance refers to the planned and systematic actions necessary to provide adequate confidence a product or service will satisfy given requirements for quality. Quality standards are critical and depend on effective policy planning, implementation and monitoring.

According to Fadipe [6] quality is the degree with which a phenomenon conforms to an established standard that makes it to be comparatively superior to others. In education, it implies the degree which an educational system adapts to the established standards and suitability of the inputs accessible for the delivery of the system. Quality assurance in education therefore means the pertinent and suitability of the educational programme to meet the needs of the institution and achieve the set objectives.

Wokocho [7] mentioned that academic institutions require qualified teachers who are well motivated. They also require quality students, conducive physical environment, well- equipped laboratories, workshops, and libraries, instructional materials in the ideal quality and quality as well as funds for research and community service.

Ojedele [8] asserts that the trend of students transiting from the junior secondary school to other levels of education has not been encouraging as it has been falling short of the expectation. He further said that, the issue of the tertiary level presents a situation that calls for concerns in terms of variation in access at the Universities, Polytechnics and College of Education and in terms of gender disparity. Implementing quality assurance techniques in education engenders a successful administration in the institution.

3. Significance of this Study

Education without vision is fruitless and education without value is meaningless. The development of a modern society depends to a large extent on the nature and standard of higher education. Quality of education depends on different issue like teacher's responsibilities and standard of teaching, educational curriculum, providing facilities and so on. The development of higher education plays an important role in facilitating these changes and producing adequately trained manpower. The effectiveness of higher education institutions contributes to development both internally and externally. So, higher and quality education needs sustenance and quality with time and space.

4. Objectives of this Study

The main objective of the study is to identify the elements contributing to the quality of higher education in Bangladesh. The specific objectives of the study are-

- 1. to identify the challenges of quality in higher education
- 2. to focus the techniques of quality education in Bangladesh
- 3. to highlight the tools for development of higher education

5. Methodology of this Study

Quality education depends on different issues like responsibilities, research and standard teaching. The study is exclusively a descriptive research and thus it is purely based on the information from secondary data sources. This present study has been carried out to evaluate quality assurance in higher education. Researcher has gained experience from Internal Quality Assurance Cell (IQAC) & The Institute of Engineering, Bangladesh (IEB) meeting and participating internal quality cell in different departments. Important information has been collected and informative data noted from expert members in different fields. Expert members have given and suggested various criteria to maintain and develop internal quality for the betterment of the institutions. Secondary data have been collected from various relevant publications and books.

6. Discussion of this Study

6.1 Higher education in Bangladesh

At present there are 135 universities in Bangladesh of which 90 are private and 40 are public. The demand for educational opportunities seems to have increased dramatically. Quality education needs to maintain all universities due to face various challenges both from home and abroad in coping with the recent world order. It needs huge component and capable human resources to face the challenges.

6.2 Quality education

Quality education is the solution to all the problems and teachers are the main ingredients in giving quality education. The quality education depends on quality classroom teaching. Standard of quality teaching depends on (a) clear tasks / aims (b) competence of the teacher (c) use of suitable teaching methods (d) meaning outcome of teaching (e) effective presentation of scientific knowledge (f) teacher's self-assessment. A teacher plays a crucial and demanding role in the process of students learning by creating a context in which the student's desire and ability to learn can work most effectively [9].

6.3 Quality assessment

Quality is not a destination rather it is a continuous journey. Quality means doing the right things right. Doing things right is efficiency and doing right things is effectiveness. The quality assurance process includes designing academic programs to measure the effectiveness and continuous improvement.

Fig. 1. Quality assessment model (developed by the author)

6.3.1 Evaluation: Evaluation is the systematic appraisal and highlighting the value of comparison against objectives and targets. It can also be a measurement of performance against a set of criterion.

6.3.1.1 Internal evaluation: It may be considered as a collective institutional reflection and an opportunity for quality enhancement.

6.3.1.2 External evaluation: External evaluation is normally carried out by a team of external experts, peers or inspectors.

6.3.2 Accreditation: Accreditation means to provide something creditable and publicly acknowledge its worth in relation to external criteria. It is the process of external quality review used in higher education to scrutinize colleges, universities, and higher education program for quality assurance and quality improvement.

6.3.3 Auditing: It is a process of review of an institution or program to determine if its curriculum, staff, and infrastructure meet its stated aims and objectives. It also focuses an accountability of institutions and programs.

6.3.4 Benchmarking: It is the process of helping compare inputs, processes and outputs either between higher education institutions or within on institution.

6.4 Quality Assurance Principles

Quality assurance system works under some principles.. The functions of quality assurance principles are given below:

Fig. 2. Quality assurance principles (developed by the author)

6.4.1 Responsibility: Higher education institution is primarily responsible for quality pledge in education through quality assurance system.

6.4.2 Spotlight: Quality assurance system should highlight on safeguarding the interests of the major stakeholders.

6.4.3 Contribution: The process of education need to be ensured who are contributed with clearly assigned responsibilities for quality assurance.

6.4.4 Purpose: Quality assurance is not only to prove anything but need to be improved.

6.4.5 Continuity: Quality assurance is a dynamic and continuous process to achieve goals.

6.4.6 Commitment: Commitment is a very essential fact and it is continuous process to improvement.

6.4.7 Organized effort: Quality assurance practices need to be initiated and managed under a structured organization.

6.4.9 Flexibility: Quality assurance needs to flexible enough to accept from a variety of internal and external constituencies.

6.4.10 Transparency: Quality assurance must be transparent in all aspects of its activities including the academic and financial matters.

6.5 Techniques of Quality Assurance in Higher Education [2]

The techniques used for quality assurance in education which is shown below:

Fig. 3. Techniques of quality assurance (developed by the author)

6.5.1 Monitoring: It is an essential source of information for programme evaluation to achieve perfect goal.

6.5.2 Evaluation: Monitoring and evaluation can help transform educational programmes and measure quality indicators toward educational outcomes, increase stakeholders participation, and empower educational leaders and teachers to build and sustain is unique, evaluators should be prepared to vary their evaluation approach based on the purpose and context.

6.5.3 Supervision: Supervision is essentially the practice of monitoring the performance of staff, observing the advantages and disadvantages with the aim of using benefits and good techniques to ameliorate the deficiencies while still improving on the standards and achieve educational goals.

6.5.4 Inspection: Inspection involves an assessment of available human and material resources in an institution have met prescribes standards, it is more of an assessment rather than an improvement induced exercise [10].

6.5.5 Internal Quality Assurance Cell (IQAC): The prime task of the IQAC is to develop a system for conscious, consistent and catalytic improvement in the performance of institutions. The IQAC will make a significant and meaningful contribution in the post-accreditation phase of institutions.

6.5.6 Quality control: Quality control cannot be over-emphasized. It is one of the techniques for establishing quality assurance in the educational system at all levels.

6.5.7 Access and equity: The trend of students transiting from the junior secondary school to other levels of education has not been encouraging as it has been falling short of the expectation [8]. Implementing quality assurance techniques in education engenders a successful administration in educational institutions.

6.5.8 Classroom management: Classroom management is a quality assurance technique used by the institutional heads to achieve quality education. Kruase et al. [3] view a classroom as where teachers create serene environment for students to know how to use the available time and resources, and also cooperate with their class mates to achieve quality teaching.

6.6 Tools for Quality Development in Higher Education

The development of the higher education institutions and of its quality process occurs at different

Fig. 4. Tools for Development Model in Higher Education (developed by the author)

6.7 Challenges in higher education in Bangladesh [11]

In the present context Bangladesh, the university education is facing some crucial challenges that can be mentioned as well as discussion.

6.7.1 Teaching Methods: Traditional teaching method is the common feature in our universities. The sharing of knowledge and students participation is very minimal. Moreover, the monologue type of teaching and learning, the traditional system of distant relationship between teachers and students act as barriers in the congenial atmosphere of free learning in the universities of Bangladesh.

6.7.2 Library and Laboratory: Library and laboratory facilities are very significance particularly in higher education. Updated textbooks, professional journals and modern equipment in the laboratory need regular research and relevant learning systems. So, inadequate library and laboratory facilities are hindering the quality education in higher education of Bangladesh.

6.7.3 Teachers and Students Politics: Both teaching and learning is greatly interrupted by the teachers and students politics. So, the respondents of the present study have clearly been identified as the major problems of his unexpected political practice in higher education institutions.

6.7.4 Lack of facilities: Facilities in higher institutions such as laboratories, equipment, libraries, journals etc. are always in short supply. Archival facilities are also lacking in almost all higher education institutions.

6.7.5 Lack of incentive for research: Teachers appointment depends on their total numbers of research papers in different categories in various fields. There is no incentive for research and publication because of accepting a few journals are not of international standard. Research papers are in very low proportion to the number of faculty due to lack of incentive for research.

6.7.6 Corruption and nepotism: Corruption is one of the barriers of higher education. Besides, nepotism recruitment of less meritorious teacher by political identities are create obstacle in higher education.

7. Conclusion

Education without vision is fruitless and education without value is meaningless. Quality is not a destination but it is a continuous journey. Quality education is the solution to all the problems and teachers are the main ingredients in giving quality education. The development of a modern society depends on a large extent on the nature and standard of higher education. Quality of education depends on different issue like teacher's responsibilities and standard of teaching, educational curriculum, providing facilities and so on. The development of higher education plays an important role in facilitating these changes and producing adequately trained manpower. The effectiveness of higher education institutions contributes to development both internally and externally. So, higher and quality education needs sustenance and quality with time and space. The teacher's participation with vision to make education meaningful and valuable will contribute to the overall development of the system of higher education of the country as a whole.

8. References

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